

CORONAD^X

COVID-19 Social media insights: assessing the potential role social media might play on knowledge and preventive behaviour during emergency periods.

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1. Introduction

Since the novel COVID-19 was first reported in Wuhan (China) in December 2019 we have seen unprecedented public health, economic and social impacts worldwide (Nicola et al.2020). COVID-19 has been an unprecedented global health emergency following the invention of the internet which has led to an unparalleled social response on social media platforms. Social media platforms have been an important public arena hosting discussions linked to the COVID-19 pandemic (Broniatowski et al. 2018). Indeed, social distancing measures applied by governments during the pandemic have encouraged more people to turn to social media and share their opinions and experiences (Lopez and Gallemore 2021). Whilst social media users should by no means be assumed representative of public opinion, it is imperative to acknowledge its critical role as a medium of public and civic discourse and engagement (Baumann et al. 2020; Mellon and Prosser 2017, Kruse et al.2017). Additionally, infodemiological (or the study of (mis)information's diffusion via digital media) perspectives on the topic suggest that the dynamics of digital discussions of specific events or momentums interact with human behaviour in complex ways (Lopez and Gallemore 2017). Hence, social media can be considered a potentially useful tool for conducting automated surveillance of emergency crises and public discourse in such crises; having the potential to provide additional means and insights to evaluate public opinion (Al-garadi et al., 2016).

This analysis focuses on exploring key themes and sentiments on Twitter's public discourse in the context of COVID-19, which has been a significant public space for discussions related to the pandemic. More specifically, the objectives of this analysis are 1) to explore COVID-19-related discussions on Twitter to identify keywords of discussions and their evolution during the different phases of the pandemic; as well as sentiment trends and patterns to better understand what twitter's online communities have cared about and what sentiments have arisen from such conversations during the pandemic; and 2) to assess the impact of digital communication and social media on knowledge and preventive behaviour during the pandemic.

The analysis has been divided into three different periods, which have been strategically selected to provide an understanding of how public opinion has evolved at key stages of the pandemic. This analysis aims to provide an assessment, within the scope of the CoronadX project, that can contribute to informing the planning, implementation, and monitoring of effective public health measures during this and future health emergencies. The main analytical strategy in this piece of research has been a quantitative approach, adopted to provide an understanding of Twitter's public discourse and sentiments concerning COVID-19 during the different phases of the most critical periods of the pandemic. The contextualization of the results, on the other hand, adopts a qualitative dimension, where the aim is to embed the quantitative results obtained from the main analysis in a review of the related work. The aim of including a summary of the related work instead has been to obtain a contextual framework for this analysis considering some of the studies conducted in the subject area. This combined approach provides not only a robust understanding of how Twitter public discourse and engagement related to the pandemic has evolved, and how Twitter users have reacted to specific events related to COVID-19, but also contributes to the understanding of the impact social media had on knowledge and preventive behaviour.

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2. Related work

Social media platforms such as Twitter play an important role in supporting people to communicate and express their feelings and emotions worldwide about various topics, including the COVID-19 pandemic. Social media offer easy access to an enormous amount of content however, it can exacerbate issues associated with misinformation and controversial data (Cinelli et al., 2020). Thus, the scientific community and governmental bodies need to understand the role social media play in enhancing our capabilities and in making a more resilient society, mostly during a time of uncertainty and potentially fake news such as throughout an emergency period. As previous research suggests, social media usage has been shown to significantly increase in cases of natural disasters and crises (Gottlieb and Dyer, 2020; Effenberger et al., 2020). With the usage of social media platforms at record levels, it is more important than ever to take into consideration public conversations and engagement taking place online to increase our understanding concerning the role social media play in societal resilience during periods of emergency and crisis.

During the 2020 global pandemic, social media has become an ally but also a potential threat, mostly when it comes to discerning fact from noise. Li et al (2020) reported that during March and April 2020, the Facebook platform put warning labels on approximately 90 million pieces of content related to misinformation like false cures, anti-vaccination propaganda, and conspiracy theories. A current major limitation of social media is the lack of ability to rapidly disseminate false information from the truth (Venegas-Vera et al., 2020; Barua et al., 2020) leaving online communities unprotected from the impact of misinformation and controversial data (Chou et al., 2018; Zandifar and Badrfam, 2020). However, during the COVID-19 pandemic, social media platforms such as Twitter have also been a source of trustworthy healthcare-related information and a guide through the pandemic phases (Holmes et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020). In this regard, social media platforms are sometimes portrayed as a “double-edged” sword with the potential to trigger disinformation, social stigma, and “othering” but also as a fact-checking source or for raising public awareness (Banerjee and Meena, 2021).

On the other hand, social media play a crucial role by providing a platform for people to share their opinions and feelings. Several studies have found that individuals can benefit from expressing their emotions on social media, connecting to other people, reducing their feelings of loneliness, and receiving social support (Akhavan Malaayeri et al., 2015; Allcott et al., 2020; Deters and Mehl, 2013). Whereas other studies have concluded that social media usage is linked to mental health problems and distress (Best et al., 2014; Hoare et al., 2016; Marino et al., 2018; McCare et al., 2017; Garfin et al., 2020); as well as to harmful and addictive behaviors

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(Alter, 2017 and Newport, 2019). Research using natural language processing (NLP)¹ on social media platforms such as Twitter has provided insight into how the online population has reacted and been affected by the pandemic and the problems related to it. Various published research studies have used these tools to investigate different aspects of how people reacted to the pandemic based on Twitter posts during the different phases of the pandemic including, sentiment analysis and content analysis (Abd-Alrazaq et al., 2020; Basile et al., 2021; Boon-Itt and Skunkan, 2020; Chandrasekaran et al., 2020; Chang et al., 2020; Das and Dutta, 2020; De las Heras-Pedrosa et al., 2020; Hung et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020; Medford et al., 2020; Sesagiri Raamkumar et al., 2020; Tan et al., 2020; Xue et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2020). There has been a commonality among these studies regarding high levels of negatively coded sentiments such as anger, fear, and sadness during the first half of 2020 which coincides with the outbreak period. The increase in negative sentiments during the first half of 2020 has also been connected to different cultural and governmental responses such as the generalized lockdowns. Surprisingly, in these studies trust was also frequently coded. Basile et al. (2021) theorized that perhaps such positive emotions have increased as a means of coping with the pandemic, motivated by the need individuals might have on trusting health institutions and governmental responses throughout the health emergency.

Other studies have tracked sentiments and emotions over time, providing insights into changes in emotions and sentiments across online communities. These studies found consistent evidence that the pandemic triggered significantly higher levels of negative sentiments and an increase in emotions connected to poor well-being such as increased stress, isolation, and anxiety, and that such emotions have become more profound as the situation evolved (Hung et al., 2020; Iglesias Sanchez et al., 2020; Low et al., 2020; Salari et al., 2020; Valdez et al., 2020). More specifically, Shah et al. (2020) found this incidence is considerably higher during the later stages of the pandemic than that reported in the very initial stages of the pandemic. Kwok et al. (2021) evaluated Australian Twitter users' sentiments concerning COVID-19 vaccination before its implementation and found that users' level of positive sentiments towards vaccines may have not been sufficient to achieve adequate vaccination coverage. Furthermore, some of these studies also analysed thematic and emotional pandemic-related content linked to people's opinions and coping strategies. Iglesias Sanchez et al (2020) found that sentiments spread dynamically across users concluding that social media channels offer the opportunity to spread positive emotional reactions by capitalising on this emotional contagion effect (Hall, 2019). However, some studies have raised concerns about the potential for harm, with this emotional contagion effect across social networks applying to negative, as well as positive emotions (Goldenberg and Gross, 2020).

In this regard, Croucher et al (2020) reported increased xenophobic sentiments and content, social stigma, racism, and prejudice towards the "Asian" communities during the pandemic. On

¹ Natural language processing techniques represent excellent tools to characterise levels of emotions and sentiments expressed among social media platform users.

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the other hand, studies focusing on thematic and content analysis of tweets during the pandemic highlighted concerns around the topics of coronavirus, economy, lockdowns, and health as prominent subjects of discussion in online communities (Hung et al., 2020; Iglesias Sanchez et al., 2020; Low et al., 2020; Salari et al., 2020; Valdez et al., 2020). Additionally, there have been several studies focusing on how different emotions and sentiments as well as content discussed on social platforms related to specific events during the pandemic, could have induced people to adopt dangerous behavior associated with health, such as the use of toxic substances (Zandifar and Badrfam, 2020); but also linked to unusual patterns of shopping such as purchasing dubious personal protective equipment (Barua et al. 2020). Barua et al. (2020) suggested that information (or misinformation) as a stimulus can alter individual responses to events. Cinelli et al (2020) have shown that the impact of information is directly related to the usage of social media. Thus, increased information consumption during natural disasters and emergency periods such as during the COVID-19 pandemic can have a significant and long-lasting impact on social behaviour and on how social media users cope with such events through their sentiments and emotions. Banerjee and Meena (2021) suggested that if social media could be channelized for information sharing whilst controlling compulsive use, identifying the vectors of misinformation, and educating the differentiation of "true-fake" news"; social media platforms could have an integrative role in public health promotion aiding global well-being and societal resilience in times of need.

3. Methodology

This section discusses the methodological issues relevant to this report. Firstly, the timeframe for the selected three key pandemic periods is described and explained followed by a description of the data gathering process, the data processing performed, and the analysis performed on the data gathered.

Timeframe²

For this piece of research, three main periods have been identified, for which snapshots of the most occurring words, hashtags, sentiments, and emotions during these three periods have been constructed:

1. The first period spans from 21 March to 21 May 2020, in which the WHO declared Covid-19's pandemic status and governments around the world imposed social restrictions as well as national lockdowns. During this period most COVID-19 cases either underwent exponential growth and daily rates peaks or flattened out for some countries in Europe. Also, during this first period, the effects of the economic impact of lockdowns began to

² The description of the worldwide events happening during the three periods analysed is not exhaustive

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be noticed. Smart working conditions are implemented where possible to reduce the impact of lockdowns on the economy.

2. The second period spans from 27 December 2020 to 27 February 2021, during which most vaccines were approved, and vaccination campaigns began across most western countries. The third vaccine dose was also authorized in Europe at the end of January 2021 and the State Aid Temporary Framework in Europe was prolonged to support national economies.
3. To conclude, the third period spans from 01 January to 01 March 2022, during which most countries have already achieved relevant immunization coverage, at least across western countries and vaccination coverage is around 75% (at least one dose) in Europe³. Furthermore, during this last period, most countries have removed all types of social distancing measures and people are getting back some sort of normality in their lives. Changes in the labour market have also started to be noticed, such as the implementation of a certain level of smart working conditions in most office jobs after the health emergency.

Data sources and methods

For this analysis, an existing Twitter dataset produced by Lamsal (2020) was used. The dataset can be found in the open-access repository portal IEEE Dataport⁴ and was built using 90 different keywords (see annex 1). The real-time Twitter feed is monitored for coronavirus-related tweets using keywords and hashtags related to the pandemic. The dataset contains over 489,000 geo-tagged tweets collected from 20th March 2020 to date. More specifically, during the first period a total of 59,554 tweets were analyzed, whilst during the second period the total number of tweets included in the analysis was 30,797. Instead, the third period analyzed only included 9552 tweets. Additionally, the dataset includes IDs and sentiment scores of geo-tagged tweets related to the COVID-19 pandemic. Twitter does not allow to share JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)⁵ of the tweets to third parties. Thus, tweets provided in the dataset must be hydrated first to get the original JSON from the tweets. This process of extracting the original JSON of the retrieved tweets is known as hydration of tweet IDs (Lamsal, 2021).

For the data analysis R studio was used to conduct descriptive statistics including content and sentiment analysis. The content analysis carried out in this report included the most frequent 20 terms used, a word cloud map, and a list of the top 10 hashtags. This technique has allowed to classify the most used words and terms and draw inferences from them on the possible topics and themes people have been concerned about the most during the pandemic. On the other hand, sentiment analysis was carried out based on emotion and sentiment recognition. This technique involves analyzing very large datasets of user comments using automated means, to extract patterns and trends in emotions and sentiments. Sentiment analysis measures the

³ European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control <https://vaccinetracker.ecdc.europa.eu/public/extensions/COVID-19/vaccine-tracker.html#uptake-tab>

⁴ <https://ieee-dataport.org/open-access/coronavirus-covid-19-geo-tagged-tweets-dataset>

⁵ JSON is an open standard file format and data interchange format that allows data interchange between web applications with servers among other uses.

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polarity of the text, by coding language to produce a ratio of how positive or negative emotion levels are. Emotions recognition on the other hand takes a step further in identifying specific emotions using the Plutchik (1980) wheel of emotions: anger, anticipation, disgust, fear, joy, sadness, surprise, and trust. Thus, each sentiment score is based on the overall vectors generated by positive and negative sentiments and the eight emotions mentioned above. For the coding of sentiment scores, the NRC (National Research Council of Canada) lexicon software was used. The NRC (National Research Council of Canada) lexicon is specialized software for studying language use and its association with the emotional states of the text's producers.

4. Limitations

This study has a few limitations that should be kept in mind while interpreting the results. Geographical boundaries were not considered when examining the tweets thus, it is not possible to attribute certain patterns and trends of terms, words, emotions, and sentiments to a specific location. Furthermore, NLP approaches do not allow analyses that consider individual-specific variables since the characteristics of the users providing the content are largely unknown due to privacy reasons. Other drawbacks of this approach include contamination of the data by both accounts and false identities. In this study, for instance, the analyses of top hashtags had to be manually cleaned and modified due to senseless and non-appropriate hashtags. Thus, we might have introduced some selection bias in the tweets we analysed. For example, the hashtags *#warningtomohamendsinsalman* and *#nofleeCOVIDAfDeatharrived* were not included but arose as the top two hashtags during the third period analysed.

On the other hand, the Twitter dataset we have used analysed only tweets in the English language. Hence, our findings may not be generalizable to individuals who do not use the English language to communicate online. Another important limitation is that our findings are reflective of Twitter users, who are familiar with social media and the use of technology. Therefore, the results might not generalize to the larger worldwide population of people who do not use Twitter. Moreover, this study has focused on exceptional world events that have involved traumatic events: findings might not be generalizable to more typical or less tragic events.

5. Analysis

This section begins with a worldview map of the tweets' location used in this analysis. The geolocation map includes the location of all the tweets published during the three periods analyzed here. A content analysis including descriptive statistics on the most frequent terms used, a work cloud map, and top hashtags shared follows. Afterward, a sentiment analysis including emotion and sentiment recognition is presented to examine patterns and trends in emotions and sentiments expressed by Twitter users over time. During each analysis, the three pandemic periods are compared and discussed simultaneously whilst the focus is to understand what Twitter users cared about and how this has evolved over the different stages of the pandemic as well as to understand patterns and trends in emotions and sentiments; trying to

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make inferences on what might have evoked certain emotional responses and trends over the key stages of the pandemic.

Covid-19 conversations around the globe

As evidenced by Figure 1 below, tweets are concentrated mostly across western countries and India. More specifically, the United States, Europe, and India are the leading locations for most of the conversations and tweets analyzed in this report. Nevertheless, the distribution of Twitter users goes beyond these three leading locations and spread all over the world. Therefore, Figure 1 reflects the locations and areas in which most of the conversations analyzed here took place between March 2020 and June 2022.

Figure 1: Worldview of COVID-19 tweets

Source: ICONS analysis from the Coronavirus (Covid19) geo-tagged tweets dataset

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Content Analysis

Figures 2,3 and 4 show the most frequent terms used in Twitter conversations during the three stages of the pandemic. As these figures indicate, the different frequencies and incidence of most terms and words used reflect the evolution and different phases of the pandemic. During the COVID-19 outbreak period or first period, terms related to the virus such as *corona* or *coronavirus* as well as terms related to the generalized lockdowns such as *quarantine* and *lockdown* dominated the social platform as Figure 2 shows. When vaccines were approved and vaccinations campaigns started during the second period of the pandemic, terms linked to the new vaccines such as *new* and *vaccine* started to be one of the most frequent terms, although most of the conversations were still predominant around the term *lockdown* during the second period as Figure 3 shows. During the third period analyzed terms related to the virus such as *corona*, *coronavirus*, or *vaccine* continue to be the most frequent terms used. It could be argued that despite the improvement of the situation concerning the virus, people's conversations were still concentrated on such issues. However, users' concerns about the virus seem to have evolved following the timeline of events and for instance, online conversations began also to focus on COVID-19 virus variants such as *new* and *omicron*. Figure 4 shows how the term *omicron* emerges during the third period. During the third period, the term *test* also emerges as seen in Figure 4, it could be assumed that the emergence of new and faster COVID-19 tests has also interested online communities.

Moreover, the usage of the term *lockdown* decreases during the third period as Figure 4 shows, which coincides with the removal of most social distancing measures put in place earlier on. There is also an important increase of interest in the term *health* over the second and third periods of the pandemic as Figures 3 and 4 show, whereas during the first period, the term does not appear at all as shown in Figure 2. It could be hypothesized that Twitter users could have become more conscious about health-related issues after the outbreak of the pandemic but also, it could be argued that people's conversations about the virus turned into discussions about how to remain in good health during this difficult period. Twitter users also might have focused on the impact of lockdowns and the virus on their communities, families, and friends throughout the three phases of the pandemic with the usage of terms such as *home*, *quarantine*, *stay*, and *people* as Figures 2, 3, and 4 show. This hypothesis might also be supported by the high incidence of the term *love* during the outbreak period when little was known about the virus, families might have been separated by social distancing measures and a high number of health-related risks and deaths were reported worldwide. An interesting trend is also observed with the term *stigma* over time; the term only emerged during the second and third periods analyzed as Figures 3 and 4 indicate. As it has been discussed earlier in this report, xenophobic sentiments and content have increased after the outbreak of the pandemic (Croucher et al., 2020) and online communities seemed to have become aware of it as Figures 2,3, and 4 show.

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Figure 2: Bar Plot of 20 most frequent terms during the periods of 21st March to 21st May 2020

Source: ICONS analysis from the Coronavirus (Covid19) geo-tagged tweets dataset

Figure 3. Bar plot 20 most frequent terms during the period of 27th December 2020 to 27th February 2021

Source: ICONS analysis from the Coronavirus (Covid19) geo-tagged tweets dataset

Figure 4: Bar plot 20 most frequent terms during the period 1st January to 1st March 2022

Source: ICONS analysis from the Coronavirus (Covid19) geo-tagged tweets dataset

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On the other hand, the word cloud maps presented in Figure 5 below provide a visual representation of the themes and topics that have emerged in the analyses. According to Figure 5, the most frequent terms appearing throughout the three periods of the pandemic were terms related to the virus itself such as words like *corona* or *coronavirus* and *pandemic*. However, at least for the terms *corona* and *coronavirus*, a lower incidence can be observed. The observed trend for the words *corona*, *coronavirus*, and *pandemic* across the different phases could be linked to the evolution of the pandemic and users becoming less concerned about the original virus and more interested in the new variants and other pandemic-related issues. In this sense, Figure 5 also shows how the word *omicron* emerges during the third period. A similar pattern supporting this view is observed with the word *new* in Figure 5. The term *new* appears across the three periods although, the frequency in which the words are being used. Whilst for the first period the word might be related to the new virus and pandemic situation, chances are the increase in its use during the second and third periods might be linked to the new vaccines, new virus 'variants', and new cures but also new ways of testing. Additionally, the higher frequency of the word *new* along with the high incidence of the words *work*, *time*, and *home* during the third period, compared to the first and second periods could also be related to the new ways in which labor markets have organized working hours. Probably, linked to an increase in smart working conditions.

Figure 5: Word cloud maps COVID-19 by pandemic key periods

Source: ICONS analysis from the Coronavirus (Covid19) geo-tagged tweets dataset

Furthermore, as with Figures 2, 3, and 4, Figure 5 shows that words linked to the generalized lockdowns were most frequently used during the second period analyzed. Although, the words *quarantine* and *lockdown* can also be found during the first and third periods with a lower incidence. The patterns seen in Figures 2, 3, and 4 for the *stigma* and *health* terms are also confirmed in Figure 5; with the two words only emerging during the second and third periods analyzed. Regarding the word *vaccines* as Figures 5 shows, is most frequently used during the period when vaccines were approved and vaccination campaigns began, as well as during the period when certain immunization period was achieved than during the pandemic outbreak period. There is also a latent trend that can be observed throughout the three periods with the words *family*, *love*, *support*, and *friends*.

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These words appeared more frequently during the outbreak period than during the second and third periods as the three words cloud maps in Figure 5 show. Even if the words *family*, *love*, *support*, and *friend* have not been the most frequently used words within Twitter conversations, not even during the first stage of the pandemic; a subtle pattern can be seen. It could be hypothesized that during the outbreak period, people turned to their families and friends to seek support and connectedness during a difficult period; thus, re-evaluating their priorities and needs. However, this pattern could also be linked to the loss of loved ones and the need for support during that period.

On the other hand, the world cloud map for the third period in Figure 5 shows that during the third stage of the pandemic, the word *death* emerges. One would expect perhaps to link such a word with a high amount of people dying from the virus, however here we hypothesized that the word *death* is connected to the war in Ukraine rather than to the COVID-19 pandemic, also outbreaking during the third period of the pandemic analyzed. Furthermore, Figure 5 indicates another subtle trend for the terms *wear*, *wear a mask*, and *mask* as the three world cloud maps show. As Gupta et al. (2020) stated, social media channels have become the most common resource for COVID-19 for scientists and the public, becoming a faster route to communicate and collaborate. As Venegas-Vera et al (2020:561) stated: “Through *social media communication*, the scientific community can collaborate around the globe in a faster way, with a decreased knowledge transition time...”. Thus, it could be argued that during the pandemic, Twitter online communities could have potentially contributed to raising awareness about preventive behaviour.

In this last section of the content analyses, Table 1 below presents the top 10⁶ hashtags used in Twitter conversations during the three periods of the pandemic, in chronological order. The hashtag is an omnipresent and dynamic annotation for social media platform users. Hashtags allow users to track ongoing conversations, communicate non-verbal cues, and signal membership in a specific community or social group. These characteristics of the hashtags often limit the insights researchers can get from their appearance. However, considering the connection some very well-known hashtags have with certain topics and social moods, it is also possible to gather further insights into the type and mood of ongoing online conversations. In light of these idiosyncrasies, Table 1 confirms the usage and evolution of word patterns and trends in Twitter conversations as seen in Figures 2-5. In other words, as Table 1 shows, most of these hashtags and their evolution of them over time are in line with the results discussed previously. Furthermore, some of the hashtags seen in Table 1 support some of the hypotheses we have formulated in this report. For instance, the hashtags *#staysafe* and *#stayhome* seen during the first and second period of the pandemic as Table 1 shows could be linked to people’s concern over loved ones and friends as hypothesized previously. Similarly, the hashtags *#faceshield*, and *#wearamask* might also confirm the role social media has played in raising awareness around certain preventive behaviours.

⁶ The column corresponding to the third period only contains 9 hashtags due to contamination data issues further explained in section 9
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Table 1: Top hashtags by pandemic period

Top Hashtags		
First Period	Second Period	Third Period
#covid19	#covid19	#Covid19
#corona	#lockdown	#Coronavirus
#coronavirus	#wearamask	#Workfromhome
#quarantine	#staysafe	#Lifestyle
#stayhome	#stayhome	#Health
#lockdown	#socialdistancing	#pandemic
#staysafe	#quarantine	#fiftharmony
#socialdistancing	#vaccine	#nowplaying
#faceshield	#pandemic	#wfh
#virus	#covidvaccine	

Source: ICONS analysis from the Coronavirus (Covid19) geo-tagged tweets dataset

Sentiment Analysis

This sentiment analysis further enriches the findings discussed in section 5.2 through the clear identification of different patterns and trends in emotions and sentiments in Twitter conversations during the three periods analyzed. In Figure 6 the percentages of tweets coded with a certain emotion during key phases of the pandemic are depicted. Overall, as Figure 6 shows, the emotions dominating most online conversations during the whole period have been in a hierarchical order *trust*, *anticipation*, and *fear*. These emotions seem to be in line with experiencing a traumatic event such as a pandemic. The most unexpected emotion could be *trust*, but as recently published evidence (Basile et. al. 2021) suggested, this result could be linked to the way individuals have to cope with adversities or awaiting unexpected events. It is also worth noticing that the most regular and with little fluctuations emotions felt throughout the different phases of the pandemic have been *fear*, *surprise*, and *trust*.

Figure 6 also indicates, against expectations, that during the outbreak period of the pandemic, which coincides with most of the generalized lockdowns across European countries, feelings of *anger* and *disgust* were less intense than during the second and third periods analyzed. It could be assumed that once the outbreak period was sort of over, Twitter users were possibly already overwhelmed by pandemic events and the impact of it on economic, social, mental, and physical well-being; and showed more often sentiments of anger and disgust with governmental and public health bodies' responses for instance than during the first period analyzed. This could be explained by all the controversies around vaccine safety as well as the foresight risk of more lockdowns and new dangers with the appearance of new virus variants as the pandemic events evolved. The trend observed for the emotion of *joy* also supports this hypothesis. The tweets where the emotion of *joy* was coded during the first period, were around 7% higher than those coded with the same emotion during the third period as Figure 6 shows. In other words, a gradual decrease in *joy* is observed over time. The opposite is seen regarding *sadness*, which shows a gradual increase over time. As it has been hypothesized earlier, misinformation and controversies around pharmacological solutions to treat the virus concerns around vaccines'

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safety along with the long-lasting impact of the pandemic on society might have wearied individuals out.

On the other hand, in Figure 7 the percentage of tweets linked to positive or negative sentiments is depicted. Positive and negative sentiments gathered are linked to emotional trends and patterns discussed in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Emotions expressed by audiences during key periods of the pandemic

Source: ICONS analysis from the Coronavirus (Covid19) geo-tagged tweets dataset

Figure 7: Feelings expressed by audiences during key periods of the pandemic

Source: ICONS analysis from the Coronavirus (Covid19) geo-tagged tweets dataset

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Thus, the percentage of tweets related to positive or negative feelings regarding the three periods analyzed is shown in Figure 7. It can be observed that the percentage of tweets linked to positive feelings is higher than those linked to negative feelings throughout the pandemic. The percentage threshold for positive sentiments across the three periods is between 57% to 65%, whereas the percentage threshold for negative sentiments across the three periods is between 36% to 42%. However, if trends of both, positive and negative feelings are considered, it can be noticed that whilst the percentage of tweets related to positive feelings gradually decrease over time, the percentage of tweets linked to negative feelings increases.

Monthly sentiment score trends over time are depicted in Figure 8. This graph represents the monthly sentiment score in percentages during the period between March 2020 and June 2022. Between March and May 2020, Figure 8 shows a trend in which Twitter users appear to feel either more positive or negative about events happening during this timeframe, abandoning somehow its neutral sentiments about the events happening around them. Between March and May 2020, a sharp decrease in neutral sentiment scores can be noticed whilst an increase of both negative and positive sentiment occurred. Figure 8 also shows a higher incidence of positive sentiment scores in Twitter conversations during the whole period analyzed in comparison to neutral or even negative sentiment scores. More specifically, there is a peak of positive sentiment scores between June 2020 and August 2020 which coincides with the removal of some restrictions worldwide, the arrival of the summer, and the relative improvement in terms of daily COVID-19 cases. Another key period concerning how sentiment scores have evolved and fluctuated over time is the period between November 2021 and June 2022. Tweet's negative sentiment scores increased by around 20% between November 2021 and February 2022. This period is linked to the need for the booster but also to the outbreak of the war. Regarding trends in positive sentiment scores during the same period, around a 15% decrease can be noticed. Positive sentiment scores flatten out after that sharp decrease between February and June 2022 but have not been back to the levels seen before November 2021. On the other hand, levels of negative sentiment scores began to steadily decrease between the period of February and June 2022.

Figure 8: Trends in sentiment scores over time

Source: ICONS analysis from the Coronavirus (Covid19) geo-tagged tweets dataset

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6. Discussion

This report provides an understanding of the topics and themes appearing in Twitter conversations as well as the emotions and sentiments linked to them during the pandemic period. The pandemic timeframe has been divided into three key periods which have been strategically selected according to pandemic key events. To this end, patterns and trends of topics and themes as well as sentiment scores coded from Twitter posts and conversations during the three stages of the pandemic have been analyzed here. Triangulation via six main results stemming from different analysis techniques showcases an empirical case for further understanding what Twitter online communities have been discussing and felt about during the different key phases of the pandemic and what emotions and feelings might have evoked such topics and themes.

The first part of this analysis shows that the topics and themes emerging from Twitter's conversations during the three periods were in line with the pandemic timeline of events, as well as the evolution of such topics with the progress of the pandemic. Topics of interest during the first period analyzed included the outbreak of the pandemic, the new coronavirus, social restrictions and lockdowns, and new health-related behaviors to prevent infections. During the second period, people continued to have discussions about the virus but social restrictions and lockdowns conversations seemed to take the lead on Twitter online conversations. The arrival of a vaccine for the COVID-19 virus was also a turning point in Twitter conversations during the second period analyzed. On the other hand, during the third period analyzed a flatten-out effect can be seen concerning the themes and topics discussed during the first and second periods. Somehow, people seemed to have gained back some sort of normality during the third period analyzed and this is reflected in the higher incidence of topics indirectly related to the pandemic such as new lifestyles or new ways of testing. Interestingly, this study also indicates that Twitter COVID-19-related conversations during the second and third periods began to focus on health and stigma issues. These results are in line with previous research, for instance, the work of Croucher et al. (2020) on the rise of stigma towards Asian communities during the pandemic or the work of Zandifar and Badrfam (2020) on the impact misinformation might have on health and healthcare-related behavior. In any case, there is little doubt that the descriptive statistics carried out on most frequent terms, words, and hashtags as well as the order in which they emerged indicate the role social media platforms play as a sharing online channel between individuals and communities. But also, as previous research has shown (Holmes et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020; Banerjee and Meena, 2021) the high incidence of some words, terms, and hashtags such as *socialdistancing*, *wearamark*, *staysafe*, *stayhome* might indicate the role social media has played in raising awareness and promoting preventive behaviours.

On the other hand, the second part of the analysis conducted here shows that the emotions leading the trends during the periods analyzed were *trust*, *anticipation*, and *fear*, which are in line with previous research findings (Abd-Alrazaq et al., 2020; Basile et al., 2021; Boon-Itt and Skunkan, 2020; Chandrasekaran et al., 2020; Chang et al., 2020; Das and Dutta, 2020; De las Heras-Pedrosa et al., 2020; Hung et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020; Medford et al., 2020; Sesagiri Raamkumar et al., 2020; Tan et al., 2020; Xue et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2020). Moreover, in this study, we have found evidence that negative sentiments and emotions such as *sadness*,

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disgust, or *anger* have become more intense as the situation evolved which is also in line with previous studies ((Hung et al., 2020; Iglesias Sanchez et al., 2020; Low et al., 2020; Salari et al., 2020; Valdez et al., 2020). In any case, our study also indicates that regardless of how negative feelings and emotions have evolved, positive feelings have overall surpassed negative feelings throughout the different phases of the pandemic. However, overall trends in sentiment scores over time show that even if positive sentiments surpassed negative sentiments, there is a gradual decrease in positive sentiments over time.

7. Conclusion

Our findings indicate that twitter's online discussions followed pandemic key events and online communities have been fully engaged with how the pandemic has progressed. On the other hand, users' emotions and sentiments have negatively changed over time, even if there was a prominent and regular positive sentiment within Twitter online communities throughout the whole pandemic period analysed. According to our findings, the prevalent pattern linked to positive sentiments found throughout the pandemic seems most probably correlated to the emotion of *trust*, which at the same time, is the positive-related emotion with the higher incidence across the three periods studied. As discussed earlier in this report, previous research suggests that the emotion of *trust* found in crisis scenarios has been linked, as a means of coping, to the motivation for individuals to trust governmental responses (Basile et al., 2021). Despite the emotion of *trust*, however, *anticipation* and *fear* have been the two most frequent emotions found throughout the pandemic. It could be argued that despite all the efforts to contain the pandemic, this has been a traumatic event and it has had a gradual negative impact on people's opinions, discourses, and emotions over time. However, more research is needed to understand any causal relationship for this trend.

More specifically, with the descriptive and visualization approaches employed in this report, this work illustrates the potential utility of social media for monitoring public discourse and engagement but also for monitoring public emotions, feelings, and sentiments during crisis scenarios in near-to-real-time. Moreover, our findings indicate that the identification of topics, feelings, sentiments and associated patterns and trends can provide pointers to how the general public is reacting to specific measures taken to tackle any specific crisis scenario. Our study also shows that observing topics of interest, variations in sentiment scores, and changes in patterns and trends via social media posts can offer a cost-effective, timely, and valuable mechanism to gauge public perceptions regarding policy and health decisions being made to address the pandemic or future similar events. There is little doubt about the powerful role social media platforms, such as Twitter, have played as a pandemic-related communication channel between individuals and communities. Additionally, this study also provides some evidence of the role social media platforms such as Twitter might have played in raising awareness and promoting preventive behaviour, which might have contributed to increasing health literacy among Twitter users.

In light of what has been discussed throughout this report, the evidence brought here and taken into consideration the scope of the CoronadX project, we conclude firstly that the study of topics discussed in online communities, as well as the analysis of sentiments and emotions'

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patterns of texts shared in social platforms; might be an important tool to measure and indicate public sentiments with regards to any specific topic in a near-to-real-time. Secondly, with a further understanding of the causal relationship between sentiment trends and topics, it could be possible to use social media monitoring activities to strategically design future communication campaigns for further promoting and encouraging preventive behaviour; whilst increasing health literacy. And finally, social media monitoring activities could help to measure the social acceptance of new health instruments or measures.

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Annexes

Annex 1

Annex 1 includes all the different keywords and hashtags used to build the dataset.

corona	#socialdistancing	#health worker
#corona	work from home	health workers
coronavirus	#workfromhome	#healthworkers
#coronavirus	working from home	#stayhomestaysafe
covid	#workingfromhome	#coronaupdate
#covid	ppe	#frontlineheroes
covid19	n95	#coronawarriors
#covid19	#ppe	#homeschool
covid-19	#n95	#homeschooling
#covid-19	#coviidiots	#hometasking
sarscov2	coviidiots	#masks4all
#sarscov2	herd immunity	#wfh
sars cov2	#herdimmunity	wash ur hands
sars cov 2	pneumonia	wash your hands
covid_19	#pneumonia	#washurhands
#covid_19	chinese virus	#washyourhands
#ncov	#chinesevirus	#stayathome
ncov	wuhan virus	#stayhome
#ncov2019	#wuhanvirus	#selfisolating
ncov2019	kung flu	self isolating
2019-ncov	#kungflu	bars closed
#2019-ncov	wearamask	restaurant closed
pandemic	#wearamask	corona
#pandemic	wear a mask	#corona
#2019ncov	vaccine	coronavirus
2019ncov	vaccines	#coronavirus
quarantine	#vaccine	covid
#quarantine	#vaccines	#covid
flatten the curve	corona vaccine	covid19
flattening the curve	corona vaccines	#covid19
#flatteningthecurve	#coronavaccine	quarantine
#flattenthecurve	#coronavaccines	#quarantine
hand sanitizer	face shield	pneumonia
#handsanitizer	#faceshield	#pneumonia
#lockdown	face shields	wuhan
lockdown	#faceshields	virus
social distancing	health worker	flu

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